

Solomon I. Khmelnik, Vitaly A. Triger

Theoretical Explanation of Patent

«DEVICE FOR CONVERTING ELECTROMAGNETIC
MOMENTUM TO MECHANICAL MOMENTUM»

Annotation

Patent WO / 2019/145942 describes a device for converting an electromagnetic pulse into a mechanical pulse, intended for use in an apparatus for flying in the air and airless environment. The article discusses a detailed theoretical justification of the principle of operation of this device, and then brief user characteristics of the device. Also, an experiment is described that demonstrates the existence of traction in the proposed device.

It is shown that **the specific thrust of this device is approximately 1000 times greater than the specific thrust of a jet engine.**

The authors offer cooperation for patenting in various countries and the development of devices for various purposes.

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PART 1. THEORY

1. Introduction

The following is the idea and some issues of the implementation of the patent “Device for converting an electromagnetic momentum in a mechanical momentum” (see appendix 1) - hereinafter the apparatus. Essentially, such a device can move in the air and airless space without using a jet engine. This implements the notorious principle of “unsupported movement” and, allegedly, violates the law of conservation of momentum. However, the electromagnetic impulse and the mechanical impulse enter quantitatively and equitably in the law of conservation of momentum. Therefore, the apparatus motion is unsupported only within the framework of Newton’s third law, which is a special case of the law of conservation of momentum. Long-standing experiments are also known [2], in particular, those belonging to well-known scientists who demonstrated a violation of the law of conservation of momentum.

However, the possibility of movement under the influence of electromagnetic forces, as a rule, is rejected. A vivid example of this is the ongoing debate around “EmDrive” [3], which shows very little force - critics are looking for some undetected forces.

Critics can be understood. The density of the electromagnetic pulse is determined through the density of electromagnetic energy W and the speed of light c as

$$J = W/c. \tag{1}$$

When dividing by the speed of light, it is impossible to obtain an impulse value acceptable for technology, and this fact convinces critics.

Umov in 1874 introduced into physics the idea of the movement of energy, the flow of energy and the speed of movement of energy. Moreover, the energy flux density S , the energy density W , and the energy velocity V are related by the formula

$$S = W \cdot V. \tag{2}$$

This statement is universal. The speed of electromagnetic energy in electrodynamics is assumed to be equal to the speed of light: $V = c$. This statement has supplanted from scientific use cases when the speed of electromagnetic energy is less than the speed of light. And such cases are known. In a static electromagnetic field, there is no electromagnetic wave, but there is a flow of electromagnetic energy. In this case, no reason to associate the speed of electromagnetic energy with the speed of light. Corresponding examples are given in [2]. In [7] it was proved that the electromagnetic pulse density of a static electromagnetic field is determined by the formula

$$J = \frac{S^3}{W^2}. \tag{3a}$$

the electromagnetic pulse density of a static electromagnetic field in a body moving with a speed v is determined by the formula

$$J = \frac{S}{v^2} = \frac{W}{v}. \tag{3B}$$

This formulas is the basis of the proposed device.

Fig. 1.

2. The design

The design of the proposed device implements this formula. It may have, for example, the form shown in Fig. 1 (from the patent [1]), and contains an energy source, an engine 110, a disk 120, and a plurality of permanent magnets 130 mounted on the disk 120. The motor rotates the disk and the magnets move at linear speed V 140. The magnets 130 have ends of the north N and south S poles. The magnets 130 are located on the disk 120 so that the planes of their ends make up a certain angle with the trajectory of the end and with the plane of the platform in which this trajectory lies. In fig. 2 shows a scan of a disc with magnets.

Fig. 2.

3. Mathematical description of the design

The Faraday unipolar induction law is widely known, applicable to a permanent magnet moving at a speed V :

$$E = V \times B \tag{4}$$

or

$$E = V \times \mu H, \tag{5}$$

where B, E, H, μ is magnetic induction, electric and magnetic intensities, absolute magnetic permeability, respectively.

The density of the flow of electromagnetic energy flowing from the end of the magnet,

$$S = E \times H \tag{6}$$

Let us consider the application of these relations to our construction - see Fig. 3. In the cylindrical coordinates r, φ, z , the vectors under consideration have the form $H = [H_r, H_\varphi, H_z]$. Moreover, taking into account (5), we obtain:

$$E = E_r, \tag{7}$$

$$V = V_\varphi, \tag{8}$$

Then

$$E = E_r = V \cdot \mu \cdot H_z, \tag{10}$$

$$S = S_z = E_r \cdot H_\varphi \tag{11}$$

or

$$S = V \cdot \mu \cdot H_z \cdot H_\phi. \tag{12}$$

This value will be greatest if

$$H_z = H_\phi = H/\sqrt{2}, \tag{13}$$

i.e. the magnet should be inclined to the plane at an angle $\pi/4$. Then

$$S = 0.5V \cdot \mu \cdot H^2 = 0.5VB^2/\mu, \tag{14}$$

or

$$S = 0.5V \cdot \mu \cdot H^2 = 0.5VHB. \tag{15}$$

Similarly,

$$S_\phi = 0.5VHB. \tag{15a}$$

The density of the entire energy flow

$$S = \sqrt{|S_z|^2 + |S_\phi|^2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}VHB \tag{15b}$$

or

$$S = VW_m\sqrt{2}. \tag{16}$$

where is the magnetic energy density of the magnet

$$W_m = 0.5HB. \tag{17}$$

Fig. 3.

In fig. 3a shows a three-dimensional image of a magnet and vectors acting on it. When moving, an electrically conductive magnet becomes an **electret-magnet**. Moreover, in it

- the abcd plane is the north end of the magnet,

- the e f g h plane is the south end of the magnet,
- the a b g e plane becomes the positive end of the electret,
- the c d f h plane becomes the negative end of the electret.

Fig. 3a.

The energy source for the entire stream with density S is the energy of the energy source for the engine, and the stream with density S is the power of the engine.

The magnet moves along the φ axis at a speed V and along the z axis at a speed V_{vert} , where V_{vert} is the vertical speed of the structure, **not** equal to V . The same speeds are the flow velocities S_z and S_φ , respectively. The density of the electromagnetic pulse is determined by the formula (3c). Taking into account (15a, 15), we find the **projections of the momentum J_z and J_φ** are equal

$$J_\varphi = \frac{S_\varphi}{V^2} = \frac{HB}{2V}. \tag{18a}$$

$$J_z = \frac{S_z}{V_{vert}^2} = \frac{HBV}{2V_{vert}^2}. \quad (18B)$$

In accordance with the law of conservation of momentum, the electromagnetic momentum in total with the mechanical momentum of the magnet must be zero, since the latter was absent at the beginning of the motion. Consequently, the magnet body acquires a mechanical momentums

$$M_{m\phi} = -\frac{HBQ}{2V}. \quad (21a)$$

$$M_{mz} = -\frac{HBVQ}{2V_{vert}^2}. \quad (21B)$$

where Q is the volume of the magnet. This impulse of many magnets is the vertical impulse of the device.

The powers consumed by the magnet for circular motion and for vertical motion are respectively equal to:

$$P_{m\phi} = S_\phi b = \frac{HBVb}{2}, \quad (22a)$$

$$P_{mz} = S_z b = \frac{HBVb}{2}, \quad (22B)$$

where b is the area of the end face of the magnet. From (15, 22) we find:

$$P_m = 0.5VHb, \quad (23)$$

From (21, 23) we find:

$$M_{m\phi} = \frac{HBQ}{2V} = \frac{2P_{m\phi}Q}{2V^2b} = \frac{P_{m\phi}L}{V^2} \quad (24a)$$

$$M_{mvert} = M_{mz} = \frac{HBVQ}{2V_{vert}^2} = \frac{2P_{mz}Q}{2V_{vert}^2b} = \frac{P_{mz}L}{V_{vert}^2} \quad (24B)$$

where L is the length of the magnet

$$L = \frac{Q}{b}. \quad (25)$$

Magnet weight

$$Z_{mag} = Q\rho, \quad (26)$$

where ρ is the specific gravity of the magnet material. The mass of the device will be defined as

$$m = rZ_{mag}/g, \quad (27)$$

where g is the acceleration of gravity, r is the load coefficient, and

$$r = \frac{gm}{\rho Q} \quad (28)$$

The power consumed by the magnet for vertical movement

$$P_m = F_{vert}V_{vert}, \quad (29)$$

where F_{vert} is the magnet traction force. In addition, we have:

$$M_{mvert} = m \cdot V_{vert}, \quad (30)$$

From (21, 24) we find the speed of vertical movement:

$$m \cdot V_{vert} = \frac{P_{mz}L}{V_{vert}^2} = \frac{HBVQ}{2V_{vert}^2} \quad (31)$$

or

$$V_{vert} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{HBVQ}{2m}}. \quad (32)$$

We find the magnet traction force at a given speed V_{vert} from (29):

$$F_{vert} = P_m/V_{vert}. \quad (33)$$

From (33, 22) we find

$$F_{vert} = \frac{HBVb}{2} / \sqrt[3]{\frac{HBVQ}{2m}} = b \sqrt[3]{\frac{(HBV)^2m}{4Q}}. \quad (34)$$

Considering also (28), we find:

$$F_{vert} = b \sqrt[3]{\frac{(HBV)^2r\rho}{4g}} \quad (35)$$

From (35) we find

$$F_{vert} = bd, \quad (38)$$

where

$$d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{(HBV)^2m}{4Q}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{(HBV)^2r\rho}{4g}} \quad (39)$$

i.e. d is also **pressure**, and traction force F_{vert} is also **pressure force**.

The obtained relations together with known external forces allow us to calculate the dynamics of flight.

Obviously, the vertical in this case is the direction of the axis of rotation of the disk. Therefore, all of the above applies to fly in any direction.

With a known traction force at each moment of time, from (35) we can find the required linear velocity of the magnets:

$$V_{min} = \frac{1}{HB} \sqrt{\frac{4gF_{vert}^3}{r\rho b^3}} \quad (41)$$

Appendix 2 describes an experiment demonstrating the existence of traction in the proposed device.

4. Examples of calculation

Example 1. Fixed and unsupported device.

The design has a disk mounted with many magnets and has the following characteristics (see PoletCEMMM.m, mode = 1):

$$b = 0.015 \text{ m}^2, L = 0.005 \text{ m}, B = 1.35 \text{ T}, H = 50 \text{ A/m},$$

$$\rho = 5 \cdot 10^4 N / m^3, Z_{mag} = 3.75 N.$$

Note that there can be many magnets and disks with magnets. Here b is the total area of all magnets. At a given speed, $V = 43 \text{ m/sec}$ according to the above formulas

$$F_{vert0} = 98 \text{ N}, r = 26, V_{vert} = 0.22 \text{ m/sec}, P_{mz} = 22 \text{ Wt},$$

$$\omega = 60V / (2\pi R) = 2780 \text{ rps}.$$

In fig. 4 shows the functions $V_{vert}(V_{vert}), P_{vert}(V), \omega(V)$.

Example 2. Counteraction to the impulse of force.

Suppose that under the conditions of Example 1, an additional force of 150 N . Find a new traction force

$$F_{vert2} = F_{vert} + 50 = 148 \text{ N}.$$

By (41) we find a new linear velocity of the magnets $V = 108 \text{ m/sec}$. Find the new vertical speed from (32): $V_{vert} = 0.3 \frac{m}{sec}$. We also find the power required for this by (29): $P_m = 75 \text{ Wt}$.

Example 3. Flying with acceleration in the absence of resistance

Consider a flight in the absence of resistance (for example, in zero gravity). Since the disk rotates, it consumes energy (22, 29) and creates a torque (30). On the other hand

$$F_{vert} = am, \tag{61}$$

where $\mathbf{a}$ is the acceleration created by this force. From (61, 29, 30) we find

$$P_{mz} = F_{vert}V_{vert} = \mathbf{a}mM_{mvert}/m = \mathbf{a}M_{mvert} \quad (62)$$

or

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{P_{mz}}{M_{mvert}}. \quad (63)$$

From (63, 24b) we find

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{V_{vert}^2}{L}, \quad (64)$$

Hence,

$$\frac{dV_{vert}}{dt} = \mathbf{a} \quad (65)$$

and rate of change of moment

$$\frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt} = m \frac{dV_{vert}}{dt} = \mathbf{m}\mathbf{a} = \frac{mV_{vert}^2}{L}. \quad (66)$$

Considering also (32), we find:

$$\frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt} = \frac{m}{L} \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{QHBV}{2m}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{L} \sqrt[3]{m(0.5QHBV)^2} \quad (67)$$

or taking into account (22b) we finally find

$$\frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt} = \frac{1}{L} \sqrt[3]{m \left(\frac{P_m}{b} Q\right)^2} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} P_m^2}. \quad (68)$$

When the direction of rotation of the disk changes, the acceleration changes sign. Thus, the rate of change of moment (68) can accelerate or slow down the device.

It follows from (61, 66) that

$$F = \mathbf{m}\mathbf{a} = \frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt}. \quad (69)$$

Example 4. Flying with acceleration in the presence of a drag force

Consider a flight with acceleration in the presence of resistance force F_T . In this case, formula (61) takes the form:

$$P_m = (F - F_T)V_{vert} = \mathbf{a}mV_{vert}. \quad (71)$$

where F is, as before, the force that a rotating disk creates in the direction of the axis of rotation. All formulas of Example 3 are preserved in this case, with the exception of formula (69), which here takes the form:

$$F_{vert} = F_T + \mathbf{m}\mathbf{a} = F_T + \frac{M_{mvert}}{dt}. \quad (72)$$

Example 5. Specific momentum and specific thrust

We find the energy that needs to be spent in order to tell the device a certain momentum. From (68) we find:

$$M_{mvert} = \int_0^T \frac{M_{mvert}}{dt} dt = \int_0^T \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} P_m^2} \right) dt, \quad (73)$$

where T is the momentum duration.

Suppose that the power P_m for increasing the momentum remains constant over the entire period T of the increase in momentum. Then from (73), we find:

$$M_{mvert} = T \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} P_m^2}. \quad (74)$$

The energy spent to get the momentum,

$$W_m = T P_m. \quad (75)$$

From (74, 75) we find:

$$M_{mvert} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} T W_m^2}. \quad (76)$$

Consider the specific momentum of our device, completely analogous to the specific momentum of a jet engine and equal to the ratio of momentum to fuel consumption:

$$I_m = \frac{M_{mvert}}{W_m/D}, \quad (77)$$

where D is the specific fuel consumption for an engine rotating a disk with magnets.

From (76, 77) we find:

$$I_m = D \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} \frac{T}{W_m}} = D \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L P_m}}. \quad (78)$$

It follows that the specific momentum increases with an increase in the mass of the device and a decrease in engine power.

A calculation using this formula (see example 1 below) shows that the **specific momentum of the proposed device significantly exceeds the specific momentum of a jet engine.**

Consider the specific thrust of our device, completely similar to the specific thrust of a jet engine and equal to the ratio of thrust to fuel consumption:

$$\Psi_m = \frac{F_{vert}/g}{W_m/D}. \tag{80}$$

We write (80) more strictly:

$$\Psi_m = F_{vert} \cdot dt / (gP_m \cdot dt/D) \tag{81}$$

or, taking into account (69),

$$\Psi_m = \frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt} \cdot dt / (gP_m \cdot dt/D) \tag{82}$$

or

$$\Psi_m = D \frac{dM_{mvert}}{dt} / (gP_m). \tag{83}$$

Given (68), we obtain

$$\Psi_m = D \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{L} P_m^2} / (gP_m) = \frac{D}{g} \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{P_m L}}. \tag{84}$$

Given (78), we obtain

$$\Psi_m = \frac{I_m}{g}. \tag{85}$$

It can be seen that the **specific thrust of the proposed device significantly exceeds the specific thrust of the jet engine.**

Example 1.

For example, if our engine is a gasoline engine, then $D=4262400$ J/kg. Let also $\frac{m}{P_m} = 0.5$, $L = 0.005 m$. Then by (78, 85), we find:

$$I_m \approx 5 \cdot 10^6, \Psi_m \approx 5 \cdot 10^5.$$

Table 1.

Engine	Specific momentum (m\sec)	Specific thrust (sec)
Gas turbine engine	30 000	3000
Liquid engine	5000	500
Solid fuel engine	3000	300
Electric Rocket Engine	50 000	5000
Ion Engine	30 000	3000
Plasma Engine	300 000	30 000
Hypothetical photonic rocket	300 000 000	30 000 000
Patent	5 000 000	500 000

The table 1 shows the values of specific impulse and specific thrust for known rocket engines [5] and for the proposed apparatus. It can be seen that the specific impulse and specific thrust of the proposed apparatus significantly exceed the corresponding values for known jet engines. This

suggests that the proposed device is an economical engine for the spacecraft

PART 2. USE

1. Introduction

The device according to patent WO / 2019/145942 is intended for use as a propulsion device for an apparatus moving in the air and airless environments. The main advantage of such an apparatus is high profitability. Schematically, this apparatus is shown in Fig. 5.

The device is built from **Rotating Disk**, on the circumference of which plurality of bar magnets are mounted. The disk is driven by a **Motor** (it is not shown in the picture) that causes it to rotate. The magnets are positioned in an angle relative to the rotation axis of the disk. When the disk rotates, mechanical momentum, perpendicular to the plane of the rotating disk is generated (as shown in part 1). This momentum acts on the disk and causes it to move along the axis of rotation of the disk.

Swivel Mechanism is needed to change the direction of flight.

Power source is needed for the motor that rotates the drive.

Fig. 5.

2. Schematic diagrams

The first circuit is described above and is shown in fig. 5. The disadvantage of this scheme is the use of a rotary mechanism that reduces the reliability of the apparatus.

Fig. 6.

Another scheme is the “flying triangle” - see fig. 6. It is a triangular platform with three disks mounted at the corners of the platform. The control system allows you to create different speeds of rotation of the disks in order to control the height and direction of movement of the disks (without changing the angle of inclination of the axis of the disk to the plane of the platform).

Instead of a single disk, multiple coaxial disk can be used.

The project offers various options for the location of magnets on the disk.

3. Features of Apparatus

1. simplicity of construction
2. reliability
3. noiselessness
4. ability to move at low speed and hang
5. ability to move in space

4. Application

1. instead of helicopters
2. instead of construction cranes
3. for the returned satellites
4. for space flights

5. Comparison with Helicopter

1. the absence of a propeller and any external moving elements; as a consequence,
2. mechanical reliability,

3. simplicity of repair,
4. noiselessness,
5. reliability.

6. Comparison with Space Rocket

1. the possibility of flying in space with low speed, and, as a consequence,
2. the opportunity of low-speed lift and landing capability,
3. low fuel consumption,
4. no overload for the crew,
5. lack of expensive heat protection.

7. The state of affairs

Designed by

- optimal shape of the magnet,
- various layouts of magnets on the disk,
- arrangement of disks in the device,
- optimal disk rotation speed,
- a way to preserve the magnetization of a magnet,
- methodology for calculating the mechanical impulse created by the engine as a whole
- methodology for calculating power consumption depending on flight speed
- methodology for calculating the trajectory and fuel consumption for the engine as a whole
- methodology for optimal regulation of speed and power,

8. Cost-effectiveness

Jet engine performance indicators are specific momentum and specific thrust. The proposed theory will allow us to calculate these indicators for our engine. In essence, these are indicators of an internal combustion engine used to rotate a disk. When calculating the indicators, the specific gasoline consumption equal to 4262400 J/kg is used. The table 1 (see in part 1) shows the values of these indicators for known rocket engines and for the proposed engine. It can be seen that the specific momentum and specific thrust of the proposed apparatus significantly exceed the corresponding values for known jet engines. This suggests that the proposed device is an economical engine for the spacecraft

9. The calculated ratio

Design parameters are:

- the radius of the disk R ,
- induction at the end of magnet B ,
- coercive intensity H ,
- the number of magnets k ,
- the area of the end face of the magnet b ,
- magnet length L ,
- specific fuel consumption for the engine rotating the disk, D
- the density of the magnet material is ρ .

It is important to note that the efficiency of the apparatus substantially depends on the length of the magnet and increases with decreasing length. Therefore, it is advisable to use thin flat magnets. Currently, film magnets exist and are being improved that are extremely effective in this application.

The calculated parameters are:

- apparatus weight m
- disk rotation speed n ,
- engine power P_m ,
- the speed of the apparatus (linear velocity of the apparatus along the axis of rotation of the disk) V_{vert} ,
- the speed of the magnets (linear velocity on the disk circumference) V ,
- traction force F_{vert} ,
- specific thrust Ψ_m ,
- momentum M_{mvert} ,
- specific momentum I_m .

It should be ensured that the speed of the magnets V is greater than a certain minimum.

The following basic relationships between the listed values were found:

$$Q = Lb, \tag{1}$$

$$P_m = F_{vert}V_{vert}, \tag{2}$$

$$M_{mvert} = m \cdot V_{vert}, \tag{4}$$

$$P_{mz} = 0.5VHBb, \tag{3}$$

$$V_{vert} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{HBVQ}{2m}}, \quad (5)$$

$$F_{vert} = b \sqrt[3]{\frac{(HBV)^2 r \rho}{4g}}, \quad (6)$$

$$V = \frac{1}{HB} \sqrt{\frac{4gF_{vert}^3}{r\rho b^3}}. \quad (7)$$

$$I_m = D \sqrt[3]{\frac{m}{LP_m}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\Psi_m = \frac{I_m}{g}. \quad (9)$$

The obtained relations together with known external forces allow us to calculate the dynamics of flight.

The vertical in this case is the direction of the axis of rotation of the disk. Therefore, all of the above applies to fly in any direction.

Appendix 1. Details of the patent [1].

DEVICE FOR CONVERTING ELECTROMAGNETIC MOMENTUM TO MECHANICAL MOMENTUM

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Applicant

KHMELNIK, Solomon; IL

Inventor

KHMELNIK, Solomon; IL

Agent

ROSENTHAL, Ytzhak; IL

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Appendix 2. Experiments

The experiment was as follows. Permanent magnets were installed on an aluminum disk in a certain way (in accordance with the patent). The disk was put on the axis of the DC motor, and the disk with the engine was mounted on a cart with wheels so that the axis of the motor was parallel to the platform of the cart - see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7.

Experience 1. The cart is put wheels on a horizontal floor. When the disk rotates, the whole structure **travels in the direction of the axis of the disk** - see the video [6] to the end.

Experience 2. The cart is mounted on the scale so that the axis of the engine becomes vertical. The scales are set to “zero”. When the disk rotates, the weight of the structure changes, which indicates the occurrence **of traction along the axis of the disk**. This experience is performed in the following options.

Experience 2a. Measurement of traction when rotating a disk **with** magnets clockwise or counterclockwise.

Experience 2b. Measurement of traction when rotating a disk **without** magnets clockwise or counterclockwise.

Fig. 8.

The measurement results are given in table 2. It is seen that

- there is a traction force of rotating magnets, independent of aerodynamic traction,
- the traction force of rotating magnets and the power consumed for this depend on the position of the magnets relative to the direction of rotation speed.

Table 2.

Parameter	Direction of rotation	
	→.	←.
Power Consumption with Magnets (Wt)	275	272
Power Consumption without Magnets (Wt)	269	261
Power Consumed by Rotating Magnets (Wt)	6	11
Tractive force with magnets (G)	430	450
Tractive force without magnets (G)	270	315
Magnets pulling force (G)	160	135

Appendix 3. Design Options

Two magnet arrangements are shown in fig. 9, where the embodiment of fig is shown on the left. 2 in the main text, and on the right is another option. It can be seen that they are equivalent in the direction of the mechanical momentum.

Fig. 9.

It follows from the foregoing that a plurality of magnets located on the platform, moving at a certain velocity, produce a summary mechanical momentum directed perpendicularly to the velocity vector. Let's consider some variants.

Fig. 10.

On fig. 10 shows an arrangement in which all the magnets are inclined to the axis OY at the same angle (similarly to fig.2 and fig.9 on the left).

On fig. 11 shows an arrangement in which adjacent magnets are inclined towards each other in such a way that the poles of the same name are adjacent (similarly to fig. 9).

Fig. 11.

Fig. 12.

On fig. 12 shows the platform P, on which the magnets are arranged fan-shaped. The platform P is moving along the axis OY with velocity V . In this case, the for magnets located above the axis OY , the north poles are located above the southern ones, and for the magnets located under the axis OY , the north poles are located below the southern poles.

We did not consider the shape of the trajectory of the platform movement - on fig. 10, 11, 12 it was assumed only that it coincides with the axis OY . However, this trajectory can be any - it is important only that each magnet is in a plane XOZ perpendicular to the axis OY . For the construction shown in fig. 11, the entire platform P must be in this plane XOZ .

On fig. 12 shows an arrangement in which the magnets are arranged circumferentially on a rotating platform and inclined to the circumference at the same angle. The velocity vector V is shown. It is important to emphasize that each magnet is inclined in a plane XOZ , perpendicular to this figure. Thus, such a construction is formed from the construction shown in fig. 10, when the rectilinear platform (axis OY) is transformed into a ring, perpendicular to the plane of fig. 10. Therefore fig. 11 can be considered as sweep of fig. 10.

Fig. 13.

Similarly, on fig. 14 shows an arrangement in which the magnets are also arranged circumferentially on a rotating platform and inclined to each other. But here fig. 14 can be considered as sweep of fig. 9.

Fig. 14.

Fig. 15.

On fig. 15 shows a device in which several platforms 1, shown in fig 12, are used. These platforms 1 are placed on spokes 2 with a common rotating rim 3. At the same time on each such platform 1 the magnets 4 are located at an angle to the plane of rotation of the rim so, that the magnets located above the plane of rotation, have north poles above the south poles, and magnets located below the plane of rotation, have north poles below the south poles.

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